

**Advantages and Challenges of Pickering Emulsions Applied
 to Bio-Based Films: A Mini-Review**

Journal:	<i>Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture</i>
Manuscript ID	JSFA-20-4306
Wiley - Manuscript type:	Mini-Review
Date Submitted by the Author:	29-Oct-2020
Complete List of Authors:	Niro, Carolina; Universidade Federal de São Carlos, Postgraduate Program in Biotechnology MEDEIROS, JACKSON; UNESP, Alimentos e Nutrição Machado Freitas, John; UFSCar CCET, Postgraduate Program in Biotechnology Azeredo, Henriette; Embrapa Instrumentação, LNNA; Embrapa Agroindústria Tropical
Key Words:	bio-based films, Pickering emulsion, water vapor permeability, active properties

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Advantages and Challenges of Pickering Emulsions Applied to Bio-Based Films: A Mini-Review

Pickering Emulsions in Bio-Based Films

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Abstract

The strategy of adding hydrophobic compounds to bio-based films (usually based on hydrophilic matrices), forming emulsion films, is a technique used to improve some physical properties (such as reducing water solubility and water vapor permeability) and/or to impart active properties, such as antioxidant and antimicrobial activities. Oil-in-water emulsions are formed by small oil droplets dispersed in an aqueous phase, and there are two strategies that can be used: conventional emulsions, stabilized by low molecular weight polymers or surfactants, and Pickering emulsions, which use solid colloidal particles as stabilizers, in the absence of any surfactant. This paper presents a review of the literature about differences and performances of Pickering and conventional emulsions as applied to bio-based films.

Keywords: bio-based films; Pickering emulsion; water vapor permeability; active properties

INTRODUCTION

Oil-in-water emulsions (O/W) are colloidal dispersions containing small droplets of a dispersed oil phase distributed in a continuous aqueous phase.¹ These systems are stabilized by emulsifiers, which are amphiphilic molecules, containing polar and non-polar regions which are positioned at the interface, in contact with the aqueous and the oily phases respectively, stabilizing the emulsions.² Emulsions have been applied in several industrial sectors, like pharmaceutical,³ cosmetics,⁴ petroleum,⁵ and food industry,⁶ among others. Emulsions have a long history of use and are widely present in many foods,⁷ including both emulsions formed by nature, such as milk and egg yolk, and emulsions created by humans, such as mayonnaise, ice cream and emulsified meat products.

In addition to applications to food, emulsions also can be applied to biopolymeric materials (whose matrix is generally hydrophilic, representing the aqueous phase). Such materials have been proposed for several applications, such as films and food coatings. In this case, the scattered phase (oily) can fulfill two main functions. One is to improve the water vapor barrier properties of films (since the matrix, being hydrophilic, does not have a good water vapor barrier). Some examples of this function are whey protein films added with rapeseed oil⁸ and pectin films with clove bud essential oil.⁹ In many cases, the hydrophobic phase added to films is represented by waxes, like candelilla wax¹⁰ and beeswax.¹¹ Waxes are especially efficient to improve the water vapor barrier, due to their high content in fatty alcohols and long-chain alkanes.¹²

Another possible function of an oil phase on polymeric films is to act as a vehicle to carry active compounds (many of which are hydrophobic), thus forming active films and coatings (with antimicrobial or antioxidants properties, among others), such as films with essential oils (EOs), which may aggregate antioxidant and antimicrobial activities simultaneously,¹³ as demonstrated in films with addition of cassia,¹⁴ clove bud,⁹ grapefruit, oregano, lemon¹⁵ and ginger¹⁶ EOs.

Emulsions are conventionally stabilized by polymers or low molecular weight surfactants, which have been extensively studied in the last few decades (Figure 1A).¹⁷ An alternative approach that has gained a lot of attention is Pickering emulsions, which are

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3 stabilized by solid colloidal particles in the absence of any molecular surfactant (Figure 1B).¹⁸
4 Unlike surfactants, these colloidal particles form a dense film at the oil-water interface, which
5 promotes mechanical barrier against coalescence,¹⁹ resulting in excellent stability,²⁰ which is
6 ascribed to its irreversible adsorption and steric repulsion.²¹ Moreover, Pickering emulsions are
7 very suitable for storage and microencapsulation of active substances, as they promote the
8 controlled release of compounds.²²
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14 Emulsion films, therefore, can also be based on conventional or Pickering emulsions.
15 This review proposes to present the main developments in emulsion bio-based films in the last
16 years, searching to analyze and identify promising directions for the development of the next
17 generations of biopolymeric films containing Pickering emulsions.
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25 **INFLUENCE OF EMULSIONS ON THE WATER VAPOR BARRIER PROPERTY OF** 26 **FILMS**

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28 Despite the many advantages of using biopolymers to produce films, there are some
29 limitations, such as their usually poor mechanical properties and high water vapor permeability,
30 due to the hydrophilic nature of most biopolymers.^{10,23}
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35 The main role of food packaging films is to protect food. In many cases, the water
36 vapor barrier property is especially important. For example, water vapor permeation to food
37 leads to texture loss in dried fruit, agglomeration in powders, and it may even favor microbial
38 growth. In this context, a strategy widely used to improve water vapor permeability (WVP) of
39 films is the incorporation of hydrophobic compounds, such as waxes, oils and EOs.
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44 The permeation of water molecules occurs in three steps: sorption and solubilization;
45 diffusion; and desorption (and evaporation).²⁴ The sorption step depends on the chemical
46 affinity between water molecules and the film matrix. The diffusion step occurs in the
47 amorphous regions of the film, and the emulsion droplets could impart tortuosity to the path of
48 the permeant molecules, reducing diffusivity.²⁵ On the other hand, emulsion droplets can also
49 disrupt the cohesion of the biopolymeric matrix, promoting discontinuities that may facilitate
50 diffusion of water vapor.²⁰ That is why the property of water vapor barrier of films do not
51 depend only on their chemical nature, but also on their microstructure.⁸ The presence of
52 bubbles, pinholes and cracks may facilitate the diffusion of water molecules across the
53 films.^{10,26} This explains why, in some cases, the WVP of films is not decreased by the addition
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3 of hydrophobic compounds, since the microstructure modification caused by these compounds
4 can be determinant.⁹ Therefore, the literature can seem inconsistent (Table 1 and Table 2) when
5 presenting reports of films whose WVP has decreased by the addition of an oil
6 phase^{8,9,30,10,11,13,25-29} alongside others in which WVP has increased by the presence of an oil
7 phase, usually at higher concentrations.^{20,29,31,32} The decreasing in WVP is mainly attributed to
8 the hydrophobic character of the emulsified compounds, changing the hydrophobic-hydrophilic
9 ratio of the films,^{9,33} whereas increasing WVP is usually ascribed to decrease in the
10 cohesiveness of the polymer network, which can facilitate the permeation of the water
11 molecules.^{20,29} In some reports,^{10,27} there was no significant difference in WVP as a result of
12 the incorporation of a hydrophobic phase, which can be explained by a combination of both
13 effects.
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23 There are still few studies about films incorporated with Pickering emulsions that
24 discuss the effects of the presence of the hydrophobic phase on the water vapor barrier (Table
25 2), some of which are mentioned below.
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29 Some studies reported positive results related to the decrease of the WVP. Danmak et
30 al. (2019)²⁵ produced gelatin-based films incorporated with soybean oil Pickering emulsions
31 (containing hesperidin as an active compound) stabilized with chitosan nanoparticles. As the
32 concentration of the oil phase increased, the WVP decreased. For the incorporation level of
33 50% (in relation to the matrix), the reduction in the value of WVP was about 31%. Xu et al.
34 (2020)²⁸ also reported a reduction in WVP for chitosan-based films with clove EO Pickering
35 emulsions stabilized with zein colloid particles. The value of WVP decreased as the
36 concentrations of EO increased. For the concentration of 40%, the reduction was around 52%.
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44 Other studies, on the contrary, reported an increase of WVP when adding Pickering
45 emulsions, especially for higher concentrations of oil phase. Shi et al. (2016)²⁹ produced
46 chitosan-based films with corn oil Pickering emulsions stabilized with zein/chitosan colloid
47 particles. The WVP was decreased about 15% for a 10% oil concentration, but increased
48 significantly for higher concentrations. Liu et al. (2019)²⁰ fabricated soluble soybean
49 polysaccharide (SSPS)-based encapsulating oregano EO in Pickering emulsions stabilized by
50 complex coacervates of acid soluble soy protein and SSPS, and observed an increase in WVP
51 with increasing EO concentrations. The WVP values grew constantly until 5% and leveled off
52 till 7% of oil phase.
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3 Almasi et al. (2020)¹³ compared pectin-based films activated by marjoram (*Origanum*
4 *majorana* L.) EO encapsulated in nanoemulsions stabilized by surfactant Tween 80 or in
5 Pickering emulsions stabilized by a blend of whey protein isolate and inulin. The WVP values
6 of the films with nanoemulsions with 5% and 7.5% of EO were approximately 58% lower than
7 its value in the control sample. The WVP values of the films with Pickering emulsions
8 decreased about 85-88% after incorporation of at least 2.5% of marjoram EO. According to the
9 authors, the most drastic reduction in the WVP of films with Pickering emulsions is probably
10 due not only to the hydrophobic nature of the dispersed phase, but also to the tortuosity path
11 created by the emulsions and to the increased cross-linking between polymer chains, causing a
12 reduced mobility, which explains the better effect of the Pickering emulsions comparing to the
13 conventional emulsions.
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23 The improvement of water vapor barrier of films with emulsion depends on the matrix,
24 the hydrophobic compound, and on the droplet sizes and emulsion stability. Furthermore, while
25 the emulsions can improve the barrier, they can also cause undesirable modifications in
26 mechanical properties or other properties of the films. Therefore, it is necessary to study and
27 understand how the properties of biodegradable films can be improved and what are the
28 properties required for each case.
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34 Usually, the addition of lipids and other compounds modify the mechanical properties
35 of films, mainly reducing the values of tensile strength, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2. This
36 is mainly due to the plasticizing effect that the hydrophobic compounds (both in conventional
37 or Pickering emulsions) cause on films, which leads to discontinuities in the polymer network.¹⁰
38 In some cases,^{9,26} however, the emulsions caused an increase in the values of tensile strength.
39 In both cases (both related to conventional emulsions), the improvement of tensile strength was
40 attributed to the chemical structure of the hydrophobic compounds used, which contain
41 chemical groups capable of interacting strongly with the polymer chains, reducing their
42 mobility.^{9,26} On the study by Almasi et al. (2020)¹³, the improvement of tensile strength of
43 films incorporated with Pickering emulsions can be attributed to the creation of new
44 interactions between the oil droplets and the pectin matrix.
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56 **EMULSIFIED FILMS WITH FUNCTIONAL (ANTIMICROBIAL AND**
57 **ANTIOXIDANT) PROPERTIES**
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3 Biopolymeric films have been commonly used to deliver active constituents, conferring
4 functional characteristics to the materials, and thereby promoting improvement in food
5 stability. In these cases, the emulsion films or coatings acting as release vehicles should meet
6 matrix compatibility requirements, be of edible origin, protect against chemical degradation,
7 have high loading capacity, high efficiency and a known mechanism of action, as well as having
8 economic viability.³⁴ Zhu et al. (2018)³⁵ produced bilayer films, one layer being based on poly
9 (L-lactic acid) (PLA), and the other a Pickering emulsion layer obtained by mixing maize germ
10 oil with a zein/chitosan complex particle suspension, containing different thymol
11 amounts. Thymol release from the bilayer films showed to be dependent on thymol loadings,
12 endowing them with antimicrobial and antioxidant activity. Also, the Pickering emulsion layer
13 lowered the oxygen permeability of bilayer films.
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23 EOs are a class of compounds largely used when it comes to active emulsion films.
24 These compounds are aromatic oily liquids derived from a wide variety of plants as defense
25 mechanisms. The EOs have antimicrobial properties, some also having antioxidant properties.
26 Incorporating EOs in films by the conventional emulsion technique leads to an early
27 evaporation of the EOs, widely decreasing their active properties along storage.²⁰ Almasi et al.
28 (2020)¹³ compared releasing properties of pectin based films activated by marjoram EO with
29 conventional and Pickering emulsion, and reported that Pickering emulsion films showed a
30 slower release profile of the EO at different incubation temperatures. That may be associated
31 with a robust layer on the oil-water interface, providing higher coalescence stability for the
32 Pickering emulsion, stronger protection of the encapsulated EO and lower release rate.
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42 Pickering emulsion films are capable of encapsulating different types of EO,
43 maintaining their activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Liu et al. (2019)²⁰
44 produced SSPS films by embedding a Pickering emulsion stabilized by complex coacervates
45 of soy protein and SSPS. The hydrophobic phase, in contents of 1-7% on a dry film basis, was
46 prepared from a mixture of EO (70%) and soybean oil (30%). Antimicrobial properties of the
47 films were evaluated (against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas*
48 *aeruginosa*) after two-week storage. As the concentration of the EO increased from 1% to 7%,
49 the inhibition areas against *S. aureus* increased more than 800%. For *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*,
50 the inhibitory ability of 5% concentration of EO was higher than the one observed for 7% EO
51 concentration, which may be associated to the early EO release from the 7% EO film, as
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3 evidenced by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showing the appearance of internal cavities
4 in the films, with a less compact structure.
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8 Valencia et al. (2019)³⁶ produced active films containing curcumin dispersed in soybean
9 oil stabilized by cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs) that presented antimicrobial activity against
10 *Escherichia coli* and also antioxidant activity. The oil concentration effected the microstructure
11 and the properties of the films. At low oil concentrations (16%), CNF and the oil interwoven
12 together, resulting in a higher hydrophobicity on the surface and increased antimicrobial
13 activity due to curcumin encapsulation. At high concentrations (>50%), a successive CNF-oil
14 layer structure was formed, resulting in a multilayered structure with oil between nanofiber
15 layers. This caused greater ductility and thermal stability, although opacity has increased and
16 antimicrobial activity has decreased. Thus, different concentrations of oil enabled different
17 types of application.
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26 Pickering emulsions as encapsulating agents of antioxidant components also show
27 promising characteristics. Sun et al. (2020)³⁷ studied sodium starch octenylsuccinate active
28 Pickering emulsion films containing corn oil and cinnamon EO (fixed concentration at 50%,
29 with different ratios between EO/corn oil). The best antioxidant properties were obtained with
30 a 4:1 EO/corn oil ratio, with 57% DPPH radical scavenging. However, when using only
31 cinnamon EO, the reduction in DPPH resulted in 21%, which was attributed to the evaporation
32 of cinnamon EO during storage.
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41 **FINAL CONSIDERATIONS, FUTURE PERSPECTIVES AND CHALLENGES**

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43 Research of films with Pickering emulsions are still relatively scarce. Further studies
44 are needed to understand the advantages and disadvantages in adopting Pickering emulsions
45 instead of conventional emulsions in films for the improvement of the water vapor barrier while
46 not affecting much the mechanical properties.
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51 In the context of their applications in films with active properties, there is a wide field
52 of studies to be explored. Some researches demonstrate the high stability of Pickering
53 emulsions to storage and their efficiency in controlled release of compounds in laboratory tests,
54 however, there are few studies in which the studies of these properties involved application in
55 food products. Likewise, comparative studies are needed to comparatively evaluate
56 antimicrobial and antioxidant properties in Pickering emulsions and conventional emulsions,
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3 in order to investigate whether the advantages of Pickering emulsions are applicable in the
4 context of films and coatings and its potential to food industry.
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8 The industrial application of Pickering emulsion films in the near future, therefore,
9 depends on several factors. The market continues to be stimulated by demands of consumers
10 that are increasingly aware of the impact of food and lifestyle on health and the environment³⁸
11 and thus looking for foods that deliver convenience, healthiness and safety.³⁹ An example of
12 an application that may be driven by the market is nutraceuticals, projected to grow 43% over
13 the next 5 years, reaching US\$ 671 billion by 2024.⁴⁰ Although little has been studied on the
14 use of Pickering emulsions as vehicles for supplements and nutrients such as fat-soluble
15 vitamins,³⁴ their application in bio-based films and coatings is a very promising research field.
16 However, further studies are needed to investigate the bioavailability and toxicity of active
17 compounds in Pickering emulsions.⁴¹
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26 It is also necessary to deeply investigate the properties of each component used in films
27 and coatings formulations, as well as their interactions and resulting structures, in order to
28 combine suitable mechanical and barrier properties to meet food stability requirements while
29 assuring a delivery of active components that is adequate to each prospected application.
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36 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

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39 The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the São Paulo Research Foundation
40 (FAPESP, Brazil, 2018/12733-6). Authors Niro and Medeiros thank the Coordination for the
41 Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES, Brazil, 88882.426523/2019-01 and
42 88882.432561/2019-01 respectively) and author Freitas thanks the National Council for
43 Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq, Brazil, 830048/2011-1) for their
44 scholarships.
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49 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

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51 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.
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16 **Figure Legends**

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19 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram of oil-in-water emulsions in configuration of conventional
20 emulsions (A) and Pickering emulsions (B).
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Table 1. Properties of conventional emulsions films

Matrix	Hydrophobic phase	Effects of emulsion				Ref.
		Water vapor permeability	Tensile strength	Elongation at break	Modulus	
Carboxymethyl cellulose		Decrease 33%	Decrease 23%	‡	Decrease 38%	
Oxidized potato starch	Candelilla wax (10%)	Decrease 42%	Decrease 57%	‡	Decrease 72%	10
Soy protein isolate		Decrease 11%	‡	Decrease 30%	Decrease 37%	
Gelatin		‡	Decrease 26%	‡	Decrease 34%	
	Beeswax (5%)	Decrease ~ 62%	‡	‡	‡	
Gelatin						27
	Carnauba wax (5%)	‡	Decrease 63%	‡	‡	
Gum cordia	Beeswax (20%)	Decrease ~ 86%	Decrease ~ 78%	Decrease ~ 84%	Decrease ~ 83%	11
Fish gelatin	Palm wax (15%)	Decrease 14%	Increase 39%	Increase 62%	Decrease 25%	26
Citrus pectin	Clove bud EO (50%)	Decrease 51%	Increase 129%	Increase 84%	Increase 24%	9
Whey protein isolate	Rapeseed oil (37.5%)	Decrease 46%	-	-	-	8
Pectin	Marjoram EO (7.5%)	Decrease 57%	Decrease 36%	‡	Decrease 13%	13
Corn starch	Orange EO (0.02%) [†]	Increase 61%	Decrease 53%	Decrease 76%	-	32
Fish gelatin	Cinnamon EO (25%)	Increase 67%	Decrease 56%	Decrease 26%	-	31

[†]Considering the orange EO density as de EO 0.845 g/mL⁴²; ‡ No statistically significant difference.

Table 2. Properties of Pickering emulsions films

Matrix	Hydrophobic phase	Stabilizer	Effects of emulsion				Ref.
			Water vapor permeability	Tensile strength	Elongation at break	Modulus	
Gelatin	Soybean oil (50%)	Chitosan nanoparticles	Decrease 31%	Decrease 35%	Increase 90%	Decrease 34%	25
Chitosan	Clove EO (40%)	Zein colloid particles	Decrease ~ 52%	Decrease 33%	‡	-	28
Chitosan	Oleic acid (150%)	Cellulose nanocrystals	Decrease 76%	-	-	-	30
Chitosan	Corn oil (10%)	Zein/chitosan colloid particles	Decrease 15%	‡	‡	‡	29
	Corn oil (30%)		Increase 28%	Decrease 24%	Increase 138%	Decrease 32%	
Pectin	Marjoram EO (7.5%)	Blend of whey protein isolate and inulin	Decrease 88%	Increase 291%	Decrease 17%	‡	13
Soluble soybean polysaccharide (SSPS)	70% oregano EO and 30% soybean oil (5%)	Complex coacervates of acid soluble soy protein and SSPS	Increase 400%	Decrease 25%	‡	-	20

‡ No statistically significant difference.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of oil-in-water emulsions in configuration of conventional emulsions (A) and Pickering emulsions (B).

254x142mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of oil-in-water emulsions in configuration of conventional emulsions (A) and Pickering emulsions (B).

254x142mm (600 x 600 DPI)